

Factors Affecting Influenza Uptake Among Healthcare Workers in a Chain of Primary Clinics in Cavite, Marikina, Quezon City and Manila During the COVID-19 Pandemic Era: A Cross Sectional Study

Elene May V. Sanchez, MD and Joseph Ivan B. Tan, RN, MD

Background: Healthcare workers (HCWs) are at most risk of contracting influenza and COVID-19 at their workplace. Despite the well established benefits and strong recommendations for influenza vaccination especially during this COVID-19 pandemic, uptake of this vaccine among HCWs appears to be low and decreasing.

Objective: This study aimed to determine the factors that affect the uptake of Influenza vaccine among HCWs in the clinical setting during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted using a self-administered questionnaire among physicians and allied staff from a chain of primary care clinics. The questionnaire consisted of multiple choice questions covering baseline demographic data, uptake of Influenza vaccine, factors affecting uptake, awareness and perceptions about vaccination. Sample size was 133, with intent to include all HCWs. Independent T-test and Pearson's Chi-square test were performed to compare the baseline sociodemographic profiles and perception of influenza. Binary logistic regression was performed to analyze the factors associated with influenza uptake.

Results: Among 143 participants, 66 were vaccinated. Occupation ($p = 0.009$) and having been vaccinated with influenza in the past ($p < 0.001$) were significantly associated with influenza vaccine uptake. Physicians were five times more likely to get vaccinated compared to Pharmacists ($p = 0.006$). Perceptions regarding influenza show no significant association with the uptake of vaccination.

Conclusion: Physicians and nurses were more likely to get vaccinated against influenza during the Covid-19 pandemic. Perceived significant exposure to influenza, with direct patient contact or care and more knowledge regarding influenza may be contributory factors. Vaccination may be included not just in company or institutional policies, but also in national health programs. Awareness campaigns can be instituted. Empathy training may help to constantly remind HCWs that they can expose sick patients to influenza and other communicable diseases.

Keywords: Influenza vaccine, vaccine uptake, healthcare workers

INTRODUCTION

In December 2019, a novel coronavirus causing respiratory illness was first noted in Wuhan, China, which eventually became a global pandemic. The virus, referred to as severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2), is transmitted through the respiratory tract and may cause pneumonia. This pandemic happened in the influenza

season and the virus causing COVID-19 has similar transmission characteristics with that of the Influenza virus. These include direct contact (human-to-human transmission) and transmission via respiratory droplet. Healthcare Workers (HCWs), as frontliners, are most exposed to these two (2) diseases. Among the preventive measures to avoid such from happening is through vaccination. Annual influenza vaccination was first recommended for HCWs by the Advisory Committee on Immunization Practice (ACIP) in 1984.¹⁵ Also, the World Health Organization recommends a vaccine coverage rate of 50%-90% for the elderly and 60% for high-risk adults. Along with other vaccine preventable diseases like Influenza and Measles, all HCWs should

^{*}Department of Family and Community Medicine, FamilyDoc

receive vaccines according to their national schedule. From a societal perspective, the total economic burden of the flu in the United States is \$87.1 billion. During influenza season it is estimated that influenza-like-illness is responsible for 45% of workdays lost and for 49% of low productivity days among working adults aged 50–64 years.

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2018-2019) flu vaccination coverage among HCWs was 81.1%, similar to coverage during the past four seasons (77.3% - 79.0%). They also reported that HCW influenza vaccination rates have steadily increased over the last decade and some healthcare institutions, agencies and systems have begun implementing declination and/or mandatory vaccination policies to further increase compliance. However, despite this initiative, studies have also indicated that HCW influenza vaccination rates remain below the Healthy People 2020 objective by the CDC of reaching 90% coverage.¹² There is no locally available data on the rate of influenza vaccination among HCWs as of this writing. Identified factors affecting uptake of influenza vaccination among family medicine physicians revealed that there is increased compliance among factors which include working duration, age, chronic disease history, and living with a person > 65 years of age.¹ In this study, the researchers further explored the factors that most likely increase the compliance of HCWs in a clinic setting to influenza vaccine.

Currently, most of the studies about Influenza uptake among Healthcare workers are in the hospital setting and there are not enough studies on the clinical setting. The study aimed to determine the factors that affect the uptake of Influenza vaccination among HCW focused on a clinical setting leading to better understanding and awareness of these factors. Moreover, vaccination is considered as one of the most effective global health interventions, responsible for significantly reducing morbidity and mortality from vaccine preventable diseases (VPDs). Recent studies indicated the importance of the Influenza vaccine on the impact of COVID-19. Thus, the result of the study is aimed to eventually be used to yield future strategies for clinicians and family medicine practitioners on increasing Influenza vaccine uptake among healthcare workers. During this COVID-19 pandemic crisis Healthcare workers are one of the most vulnerable and affected professions as they are the one mainly dealing with the crisis thus frontline healthcare workers are often recommended to get flu vaccination. Increasing understanding of the factors on the uptake of Influenza vaccine among them can potentially lead to future programs and strategies that can deal with it thus decreasing the impact of COVID-19 and Influenza to HCW.

This study aimed to determine the factors influencing Influenza vaccine uptake among healthcare workers (HCWs) in a primary care setting during the COVID-19 pandemic era.

METHODS

Study Design, Duration and Setting

This cross-sectional study was conducted from August to September 2020. The participants in this study were active HCWs from Cavite, Marikina, Quezon City and Manila. The aforementioned chain of family clinics is community-based that provides primary healthcare services to middle-income families. It is divided into regions of South 1

(Cavite), South 2 (Paranaque, Laguna, Las Pinas), East (Taguig, Pasig, Rizal) and North (Manila, Marikina and Quezon City). The outpatient clinic offers the influenza vaccination for indicated patients as well as HCWs.

The participants were either those who had received and not received the influenza vaccine from March to August 2020, and who consented to participate in the study. A total of 143 out of 267 self-administered questionnaires distributed to the HCWs in the North and South 1 regions were answered, with 54% response rate. Computed sample size was 133 using G*Power 3.1 statistics, with 95% confidence interval, power of 80%, effect size of 0.3, DF of 4. Only fully completed questionnaires were used for data analysis.

Study Population

The study included Family and Community Medicine residents and allied healthcare workers employed in a Primary Care clinic in Cavite, Markina, Quezon City and Manila on the period date of the study. Allied healthcare workers included the nurses, pharmacists, radiology technicians, and clinic assistants.

Excluded were those who have known allergies to the Influenza vaccine and its contents and those who refused to participate in the study. Healthcare workers in the clinics but are employed under a third party agency were excluded as well.

Data Collection and Outcome Measurement

Data Collection

This study utilized a self-administered questionnaire asking about the Influenza vaccine uptake of active HCWs of the clinic, from March to August 2020, alongside its related factors. Vaccine uptake includes schedule completion, initiation of vaccine course and up-to-date with coverage of the vaccine. Questions used were patterned from earlier studies examining Influenza vaccine compliance were utilized as the basis for the questionnaire. Questions that are specific to the purposes of this study were also added. The questionnaire was divided according to the following: a) baseline demographic data b) uptake of the Influenza vaccine from March to August 2020, c) possible factors affecting uptake d) awareness and perceptions about vaccination.

Data Analysis

MS Excel and IBM SPSS Statistics were the software applications used in performing the statistical analyses. Baseline characteristics and clinic findings were presented using frequency and percentage for categorical variables, and mean and standard deviation for numerical variables. Independent T-test and Pearson's Chi-square test were performed to compare the baseline sociodemographic profiles among HCWs and perception of influenza among those vaccinated against those who were not vaccinated for the Influenza vaccine. To further analyze the factors associated with influenza uptake, binary logistic regression was performed. A p-value of <0.05 was considered to indicate statistical significance.

Ethical Considerations

During data collection, the researchers requested participants to sign a consent form first before proceeding to answer the questionnaires attached next to it. The form also stated the objectives of the study, associated risks and benefits, confidentiality of records, the researchers' contact details, and a statement that participation is voluntary. For confidentiality and security of information, the data collected from the participants and their identities will be kept strictly confidential. Physical data will be stored for one year after the conclusion of the research and will eventually be shredded. Meanwhile, electronic data will be stored in a secure computer. Each participant will be provided a code number to ensure anonymity.

Each participant was informed of the goals and design of the study through the informed consent. It was further stressed that the study will not expose patients to danger and that they are also free to withdraw from the study at any time. The results produced through this study will solely be used to contribute to raising awareness on the importance of Influenza vaccination for healthcare workers. This research was granted approval for implementation after being reviewed by members of the company's management team, together with the Legal Officer, and Data Privacy Officer.

RESULTS

A total of 267 participants were recruited, and among these, 143 consented to be included in the study. Only 66 (46%) of the respondents were vaccinated against Influenza. As seen in Table 1, the mean age

for vaccinated (31.11, ± 3.81) and not vaccinated (31.15, ± 5.25) individuals were almost the same ($p=0.792$). Among the 143 participants, most were nurses (35.66%) and physicians (26.57%), female (75.3%), single (67.13%), had an income of $>10,000$, more than 1 year in work (54.55%) and were not living with elderly (71.33%). Occupation ($p=0.009$) and previous uptake of flu vaccine ($p<0.001$) were significantly associated with influenza vaccine uptake during the pandemic. Sex, marital status, number of years of work, status of living with elder and presence of co-morbidities were not. Most common comorbidities were Asthma and Hypertension.

On their perception regarding Influenza vaccines, HCW participants who were vaccinated and not vaccinated perceived vaccination as susceptible (63.64%), beneficial (97.20%), accessible (78.85%) and affordable (57.69%). Fears related to vaccination were responded by 17.31% participants. Results showed no significant association between perception regarding influenza and uptake of vaccination.

Regression analysis (Table 3) shows that occupation and flu vaccination in the past were shown to have significant associations with the uptake of influenza vaccination during the pandemic. Physicians were almost five (5) times more likely to get vaccinated as compared to Pharmacists. ($p=0.006$). Nurses were almost two (2) times more likely to get vaccinated as compared to Pharmacist while Clinic Assistant and RadTech were less likely to get vaccinated as compared to Pharmacist, however, it is not statistically significant. Those who were vaccinated in the past are four (4) times more likely to be vaccinated versus those who did not have prior vaccination.

Table 1. Comparison of baseline sociodemographic profiles among HCWs in primary care clinics among those vaccinated against those who were not vaccinated for influenza vaccine.

Profile	Total (N=143)		Vaccinated (N=66)		Not Vaccinated (N=77)		p-value
Age (Mean, SD)	31.26	± 5.35	31.39	± 5.49	31.15	± 5.25	0.792
Sex							
Male	35	24.48	14	21.21	21	27.27	0.401
Female	108	75.52	52	78.79	56	72.73	
Marital Status							
Single	96	67.13	42	63.64	54	70.13	0.410
Married	47	32.87	24	36.36	23	29.87	
Separated	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	
Occupation Category							
Physician	38	26.57	26	39.39	12	15.58	0.009
Nurse	51	35.66	24	36.36	27	35.06	
Clinic assistant	18	12.59	5	7.58	13	16.88	
Rad Tech	11	7.69	3	4.55	8	10.39	
Pharmacist	25	17.48	8	12.12	17	22.08	

Monthly Personal Income							
Less than 10,000	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	-
More than 10,000	143	100.00	66	100.00	77	100.00	
Numbers of Years at Work							
≤ 1 year	65	45.45	31	46.97	34	44.16	0.736
>1 year	78	54.55	35	53.03	43	55.84	
Comorbidities							
Hypertension	9	6.29	4	6.06	5	6.49	0.915
Diabetes	1	0.70	0	0.00	1	1.30	0.353
Asthma	14	9.79	6	9.09	8	10.39	0.794
Dyslipidemia	3	2.10	1	1.52	2	2.60	0.653
Others	6	4.20	5	7.58	1	1.30	0.062
Living with Elderly							
Yes	41	28.67	16	24.24	25	32.47	0.278
No	102	71.33	50	75.76	52	67.53	
Flu Vaccinated in the Past							
Yes	85	59.44	51	77.27	34	44.16	<0.001
No	45	31.47	10	15.15	35	45.45	
Not sure	13	9.09	5	7.58	8	10.39	

Table 2. Comparison of influenza vaccination uptake among healthcare workers based on perception regarding influenza vaccine, in a chain of family clinics in Cavite, Markikina, Quezon City and Manila for the year 2020.

Perception	Total (N=143)		Vaccinated (N=66)		Not Vaccinated (N=77)		p-value
Perceived Susceptible							
Yes	91	63.64	48	72.73	43	55.84	0.096
No	26	18.18	10	15.15	16	20.78	
Not sure	26	18.18	8	12.12	18	23.38	
Perceived Beneficial							
Yes	139	97.20	65	98.48	74	96.10	0.0418
No	2	1.40	0	0.00	2	2.60	
Not sure	7	4.90	1	1.52	1	1.30	
Perceived Accessible							
Yes	123	86.01	61	92.42	62	80.52	0.096
No	13	9.09	4	6.06	9	11.69	
Not sure	7	4.90	1	1.52	6	7.79	
Perceived Affordable							
Yes	90	62.94	48	72.73	42	54.55	0.053
No	40	27.97	15	22.73	25	32.47	
Not sure	13	9.09	3	4.55	10	12.99	
Fear Related to Vaccination							
Yes	27	18.88	8	12.12	19	24.68	0.056
No	116	81.12	58	87.88	58	75.32	

Table 3. Regression analysis on the factors associated with influenza vaccine uptake among HCWs in a chain of family clinics located in Cavite, Marikina, Quezon City and Manila

Occupation	B	S.E.	Wald	Sig.	dds Rat	95% CI	
Physician	1.527	0.553	7.629	0.006	4.604	1.558	13.606
Nurse	0.636	0.512	1.541	0.215	1.889	0.692	5.156
Clinic Assistant	-0.202	0.679	0.088	0.766	0.817	0.216	3.091
RadTech	-0.227	0.801	0.080	0.777	0.797	0.166	3.833
Constant (Pharmacist)	-0.754	0.429	3.091	0.079	0.471		
Flu Vaccinated in the Past							
Yes	1.453	0.374	15.086	<0.001	4.274	2.054	8.897
Not sure	-0.378	0.381	0.986	0.321	0.685	0.325	1.445
Constant	-0.924	0.324	8.116	0.004	0.397		

DISCUSSION

During this COVID-19 pandemic and Influenza season, HCWs as front liners are most exposed to these two diseases. Influenza vaccination has been an established preventive strategy against influenza illness among HCWs. Despite the fact that HCWs vaccination against influenza results in improved patient and employee safety, and health-care expenditures, the majority of HCWs remain unvaccinated, as mirrored in this study. The results of this study show occupation and previous Influenza vaccination significantly influenced vaccination uptake. The results can be interpreted such that vaccination uptake of physicians may have been affected and influenced by their in-depth knowledge regarding influenza and the benefits of vaccination, especially in this pandemic. Moreover, physicians and nurses are the most exposed and have consistent and direct interaction with patients, hence they were more likely to get vaccinated in order to protect them. This has been reflected as well in a study wherein significant differences at the levels of vaccine acceptance are found among professions, and are attributed to different levels of knowledge or motivation for vaccination ($p < 0.001$).⁸ In this study, Clinic Assistants and Radiology Technicians were less likely to be vaccinated. Same findings were noted in two (2) previous studies in which the proportion of medical and nursing staff vaccinated was significantly lower than the other groups, and that of five (5) occupational categories of HCWs, health aids had the lowest odds ratio for being vaccinated against Influenza ($p < 0.01$).^{3,6} On the other hand, findings of this study were found to be different from other studies which found no significant association seen for the occupation category.^{9,12}

In terms of previous vaccine uptake, the findings in this study were congruent with those in a research in which influenza vaccination was the strongest prognostic factor for vaccine uptake among HCWs, and indicates a positive attitude towards influenza vaccination enhanced yearly uptake ($p < 0.001$).⁸ This may be due to the fact that their previous vaccination gave them a sense of being protected since HCWs have higher risk for contracting influenza because of the nature of the work, especially during this pandemic.⁵

Also in another research, the investigators found the most common reason given (96% of vaccine recipients) was to protect themselves against influenza infection.¹¹

However, contrary to a previous study wherein perceived beneficial and susceptible of HCWs were significantly associated with vaccine uptake, this study found otherwise.⁸ This may be due to low awareness of the possible benefits of vaccination as well as the grave complications of the disease and its economic impact. From this perspective, all the initiatives and strategies adopted in healthcare contexts to improve influenza vaccination knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions could contribute to an improvement in vaccine uptake.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study recommends that influenza vaccination be made mandatory if with proper assessment and review of policies. The vaccination coverage can be increased by providing guidance for the planning and organization of seasonal and perennial influenza campaigns or awareness. Promotion may be carried out through, awareness campaign on the benefits of vaccination and accessibility. Health institutions should ensure accessibility of vaccines to HCWs are prioritized first due to risk of exposure. In relation to that, healthcare employers can improve voluntary uptake of vaccination by HCWs, by providing vaccines without charge at convenient times and locations. The highest rates of vaccination are in settings that require it as a condition of employment.

Since physicians have greater knowledge about Influenza vaccination, another recommendation to promote vaccination among HCWs. Influenza vaccine promotion efforts encourage more knowledgeable HCWs to set an example for other HCWs, and even non-HCWs. Empathy training would be an appropriate intervention to constantly remind HCWs that they can expose sick patients to influenza, as well as various communicable diseases. Adding an education intervention aimed at increasing knowledge on the benefits, such as the loss of sick days as a result of influenza.

In spite of these recommendations, hesitancy in uptake of vaccine may remain relatively high among HCWs unless there is a greater threat

of morbidity or mortality associated with the influenza, and now linked with complications of COVID-19 infection.

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